

Template for dissemination of scientific results

Scientific topic: Test of Doppler lidar configurations for wind retrieval

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Abstract: Currently, operators of Doppler lidars have a variety of options of setting up their scan pattern, to measure wind. Here, we test different conical scan configurations with a varying number of fixed directions are tested under the same atmospheric conditions. As reference instruments, we utilize the radar wind profiler and the radiosonde. All instruments are located at the Lindenberg Meteorological Observatory. The data is processed with the help of the existing Doppler lidar toolbox. The analysis looks in different altitude regimes and the mean squared deviation, the mean absolute deviation and the mean deviation are calculated. The outcome will give new and old users of Doppler lidars advice on how to setup their systems in regards of the expected uncertainties. A widespread use of similar scanning strategies ensures comparability within decentralized networks, which has impacts on NWP and scientific studies. While the report on the overall results serves as a direct deliverable, the results of this VM should be part of a publication to enhance the visibility of CA18235's outcomes.

Links: https://github.com/mkay-atm/dl_toolbox

Figures:

Table 1: Instrument serial number, system type, and implemented number of directions N_v of Doppler lidar systems used for the comparison of different VAD scan configurations.

serial number	system type	number of directions N_v
249	Stream Line XR	6
248	Stream Line XR+	8
44	Stream Line XR	12
234	Stream Line XR	12
233	WindCube 200S	24

Figure 1: Mean square deviation for corrected data sets with the RWP as a reference.

1 Introduction

To determine the three-dimensional wind vector it is necessary to either set up at least three Doppler lidars (DL) looking at a single point or to implement a suitable scan mode geometry in order to obtain at least three spatially different measurements within a short time span [Teschke, G. and Lehmann, V., 2017]. The velocity azimuth display (VAD) is a conical scan pattern, where the elevation angle is fixed and the azimuth angle is variable while the number of individual beam directions can be specified by the operator [Foken, 2021].

Because the atmospheric state is constantly changing and because a single line of sight (LOS) measurement takes a finite amount of time, the optimal number of fixed VAD directions is crucial for operational applications of DLs, e.g. as part of a future network of DLs within Germany. Here, [Teschke, G. and Lehmann, V., 2017] employ mathematical reasoning and suggest using a larger number of beam directions, because it appears to be beneficial regarding the reduction of error variance. Contrary to that, [Rahlvcs et al., 2022] state that a VAD 6 scheme proves superior to VAD 24 in most cases.

[Rahlvcs et al., 2022] performed virtual DL measurements within a large eddy simulation, while [Teschke, G. and Lehmann, V., 2017] approach the problem using an explicit algebraic solution. Since there are no actual comparisons based on observational data to date, side-by-side measurements of five DLs with different VAD scan configurations are compared under the same atmospheric conditions in the period from January 26 and February 28, 2023. All instruments are located at the Lindenberg Meteorological Observatory. As reference instruments, we utilize the radar wind profiler and the radiosonde. The data is processed with the help of the existing Doppler lidar toolbox. The analysis looks in different altitude regimes and the mean squared deviation is used as a metric.

The results can give new and old users of Doppler lidars advice on how to set up their systems to minimize the error in their wind retrieval and can facilitate the use of Doppler wind lidar data processing leading to a wider use of the data, common scanning strategies, operationality, comparability and ingestion into NWP models, and through that, towards a higher impact of each single measurement.

2 VAD Scan Technique

For operational meteorology it is practical to use scan techniques such as the VAD [Teschke, G. and Lehmann, V., 2017]. The wind velocity and direction is described by the wind vector $\mathbf{v} = (u, v, w)$ composed of the two horizontal components u and v and the vertical component w [Foken, 2021]. The VAD scan technique relies on the assumption that the horizontal wind speed is homogeneous over the atmospheric volume and stationarity for the duration of the scan i.e. $\mathbf{v}(x, y, z, t) \approx \mathbf{v}(z)$ [Rahlvcs et al., 2022]. The measured radial wind vector \mathbf{V}_r for the distance r from the instrument is the list of projections of the wind vector \mathbf{v} onto the unique LOS directions.

Figure 1: Exemplary scheme of the VAD scan technique for $n=12$ different azimuth directions with azimuth angles α . The beam points upwards with an elevation angle ϵ . The red volumes represent the tested atmospheric volumes with a range ΔR with r being the LOS distance to the instrument. Taken from [Päschke et al., 2015].

The projection matrix is:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \sin(\alpha_1) \sin(\Phi) & \cos(\alpha_1) \sin(\Phi) & \cos(\Phi) \\ \sin(\alpha_2) \sin(\Phi) & \cos(\alpha_2) \sin(\Phi) & \cos(\Phi) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \sin(\alpha_n) \sin(\Phi) & \cos(\alpha_n) \sin(\Phi) & \cos(\Phi) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of azimuth directions N_v . We then get an overdetermined linear system:

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{V}_r. \quad (2)$$

The least square solution can be described by:

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{A}^+ \mathbf{V}_r = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{D}^{-1}\mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{V}_r. \quad (3)$$

A detailed derivation of Equation 3 can be found in [Päschke et al., 2015].

3 Data Set

The VAD scanning technique relies on the assumption of a horizontally homogeneous wind field and stationarity for the duration of the scan. The number of azimuth angles N_v may influence whether these conditions are violated in reality or not. When using a high number of azimuth angles, the system takes longer to complete a full round of measurements. In this case, the assumption of stationarity might not be met [Rahives et al., 2022]. On the other hand, more data points are taken into account when averaging, which might minimize the error and lead to a more reliable result [Teschke, G. and Lehmann, V., 2017]. Hence, the number of beam directions is an important parameter that leaves room for improvement.

To analyze if there is a superior number N_v that should be chosen when executing DL wind measurements using VAD retrieval, five DLs with different configurations regarding the number of directions were set up for wind measurements. The different systems with

their serial number and number of directions can be found in Table 2. All instruments are located at the Lindenberg Meteorological Observatory, measuring under the same atmospheric conditions. The DLs used for the measurement are pulsed coherent instruments and operate using heterodyne detection.

Table 1: Instrument serial number, system type, and implemented number of directions of DL systems used for the comparison of different VAD scan configurations.

serial number	system type	number of directions N_v
249	Stream Line XR	6
248	Stream Line XR+	8
44	Stream Line XR	12
234	Stream Line XR	12
233	WindCube 200S	24

The data covers the period from January 25 to February 28, 2023. All scans were performed with an elevation angle $\epsilon = 75^\circ$ and 30000 pulses, except DL 234 that averaged 10000 pulses.

The DL data is processed using DWD’s DL toolbox. This enables quasi-operational data acquisition and quality controlled data ¹. As quality control parameters the coefficient of determination, the CN for collinearity diagnostics, and a threshold for the number of available directions $N_{v_{rad}}$ are applied. In our case only lidar measurements, that pass the following quality control parameters are used: $R^2 > 0.95$, $CN < 10$, and $N_{v_{rad}} > 12$. Together with a consensus threshold of $N_t = 60\%$ and a radius of $r_{CNS} = 3\frac{m}{s}$.

As reference instruments a 482 MHz radar wind profiler and the Vaisala radiosonde RS41 are utilized. The radar wind profiler (RWP) is a pulsed coherent Doppler radar with an antenna pointing in five directions and an additional RASS [DWD].

At the end of January and during February 2023 the boundary layer (BL) was as profound as one would expect during winter with an average range of about 1km. At the same time, the instrument’s range was not limited by a lot of cloud cover, making measurements in the free troposphere (FT) possible. The wind speed range goes beyond $60\frac{m}{s}$ in the FT and even in the BL wind speeds of about $30\frac{m}{s}$ are reached. The first range goes up to 2 km which corresponds to the BL, covering a region where data availability is high due to a high particle concentration in the atmosphere. The second height range reaches from 2km to 4km with a rather small data availability and therefore a generally higher mean square error (MSE). Due to higher cloud coverage between 4km and 6km, the data availability increases again while the MSE decreases. Above 6km the data is statistically not relevant with a low number of data points. Those changes in data availability and MSE depending on the height can be retraced in Figure 2, where both quantities are depicted exemplary for the DL 44. The plots for the other systems would look similar.

¹https://github.com/mkay-atm/dl_toolbox

Figure 2: MSE (black) and number of data points (blue) as a function of height exemplary for the DL 44.

The comparability of the DLs can be impaired by different effects. An example being the DL 234 where an elevation offset was found in previous work. To improve the comparability among the data sets a linear fit indicating each deviation with respect to the RWP data is calculated, exemplarily depicted in Figure 3 for the DL 234. The fit parameters in Table 2 are used to correct all data points. This way, the bias effect is minimized.

Figure 3: Depiction of wind speed differences $\Delta v_{RWP,DL234}$ as a function of RWP measured wind speeds. The green line represents the linear fit function with parameters $m = -0.056$ (slope) and $b = 0.045 \frac{m}{s}$ (intercept).

serial number	linear fit
44	$0.005 \cdot v + 0.066 \frac{m}{s}$
234	$-0.056 \cdot v + 0.045 \frac{m}{s}$
248	$-0.012 \cdot v + 0.008 \frac{m}{s}$
249	$-0.025 \cdot v - 0.148 \frac{m}{s}$
233	$0.020 \cdot v + 0.060 \frac{m}{s}$

Table 2: Linear fit parameters for DL systems with the RWP as a reference.

The same procedure is conducted with the radiosonde (RS) as a reference. Those fit

parameters can be found in Table 3.

serial number	linear fit
44	$-0.020 \cdot v + 0.442 \frac{m}{s}$
234	$-0.065 \cdot v + 0.114 \frac{m}{s}$
248	$-0.039 \cdot v + 0.343 \frac{m}{s}$
249	$-0.041 \cdot v + 0.037 \frac{m}{s}$
233	$0.009 \cdot v + 0.125 \frac{m}{s}$

Table 3: Linear fit parameters for DL systems with the RS as a reference.

4 Assessment of VAD-Scan Variations

To analyze if there is an optimal number N_v that should be chosen when executing DL wind measurements using VAD retrieval, five Doppler lidars (DL) with different configurations regarding the number of directions were set up for wind measurements. The expected errors are quantified and compared in the following.

Accordingly to the altitude ranges described in Section 3, the data sets are subdivided into three regimes (0-2km, 2-4km and 4-6km). To compare the data the MSE for each data set was calculated. The results are depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: MSE for corrected data sets with the RWP as a reference.

Of the four configurations examined, the VAD 12 and VAD 24 schemes yield the smallest wind speed MSE in all three height ranges. The data retrieved using the VAD 8 scheme results in a higher MSE and VAD 6 performs even worse. When using VAD the windspeed MSE is about twice as high as for VAD 12 and VAD 24.

To illustrate the influence of the applied correction, the results using the uncorrected data are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: MSE for uncorrected data sets with the RWP as a reference.

The same evaluation is carried out using the RS data as a reference. Again, a linear fit is calculated indicating each deviation with respect to the RS data to achieve a better comparability among the data sets.

The MSE is calculated for the different VAD configuration in each altitude regime. The results can be found in Figure 6.

Figure 6: MSE for corrected data sets with the RS as a reference

Figure 6 shows a similar result. In all three altitude regimes VAD 12 and VAD 24 yield the smallest wind speed MSE while VAD 6 performs worst.

The results using the uncorrected data can be found in Figure 7.

Figure 7: MSE for uncorrected data sets with the RS as a reference.

5 Conclusion and Outlook

VAD Scan variations are analyzed using the data collected by five DL systems measuring with 6, 8, 12 or 24 directions. To achieve better comparability among the instruments, all data sets are adjusted to the RWP or RS as references by fitting a linear function and correcting the data accordingly. One can find that VAD 12 and 24 yield a smaller MSE than VAD 6 and 8, matching the results of [Teschke, G. and Lehmann, V., 2017]. The results disagree with [Rahlves et al., 2022], where it is stated that poor performance of horizontal wind speed measurements is found for the VAD 24 scheme in conjunction with an elevation of 75° and that in most of the analyzed cases, the VAD 6 proves superior to VAD 24 for horizontal wind speed measurements. Further, the results presented here suggest that 12 directions perform as good as 24. Hence, this study recommends 12 directions for use in operational networks. But in this regards, additional experiments should be performed. It would be interesting to extend the study, setting up even more DL systems and testing for a higher variety of numbers of directions e.g. also for 10, 16, and 20 as well as different elevation angles.

6 Bibliography

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